

Synthesis and Reactions of some New Benzimidazoles. Part-II

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Interaction of (*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)acetic acid hydrazide (1) with isothiocyanates affords acetylthiosemicarbazides (2a-c) which on cyclisation give 3a-c. Reaction of 3a with alkyl halide, ethyl chloroacetate and/or diethyl bromomalonate affords *S*-alkyl derivatives (4a-e). Condensation of 3a with *p*-substituted-phenacyl bromides gives 5a-c. Treatment of 3a with *N*-aryl and *N*-heterocyclic-2-chloroacetamides gives 6a-c. Reaction of 3a with CH₂O in the presence of morpholine or *p*-toluidine affords the Mannich bases (7a,b). Cyclodehydration of 2a-c with phosphoric acid gives the thiadiazoles (8a-c). Interaction of 1 with CS₂ gives 9 which is reacted with hydrazine hydrate to give 10. Condensation of 10 with aromatic aldehydes gives the azines (11a-f). Reaction of 10 with *p*-substituted-phenacyl bromide gives the uncyclised products 12a-c rather than cyclised ones 13a-c. Several compounds are screened for antibacterial activities.

The diverse pharmacological activities of many benzimidazoles stimulated our interest for the synthesis of various derivatives of this ring systems. In continuation of our previous work¹, the present investigation involves synthesis of some new heterocyclic compounds derived from (*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)acetic acid hydrazide (1).

Substituted thiosemicarbazides are known to possess interesting biological properties². On these findings a systematic study of thiosemicarbazides of the type 2 was of interest as they themselves may show biological properties and also being active intermediate in the synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives bearing different heterocyclic rings at their 2-position. The latter ones were reported to exhibit a broad spectrum biological effects³.

To accomplish this goal, (*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)acetyl thiosemicarbazides (2a-c) were prepared by the reaction of (*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)acetic acid hydrazide (1) with isothiocyanate derivatives in refluxing ethanol. Cyclisation of 2a-c under alkaline conditions gave 5-[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-4-alkyl/phenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiols (3a-c).

Interaction of 3a with alkyl halides, ethyl chloroacetate and/or diethyl bromomalonate in basic medium gave the corresponding *S*-alkyl derivatives (4a-e) in moderate yields. On the other hand, condensation of 3a with the appropriate *p*-substituted-phenacyl bromide in ethanol either in pres-

ence or absence of sodium acetate afforded compounds 5a-c.

Moreover, simple and heterocyclic amides are known to possess interesting biological properties, therefore, inclusion of amide moiety at 5-position of compound 3a might enhance the biological activity. Condensation of 3a with *N*-aryl/heterocyclic-2-chloroacetamides was undertaken with the hope that the new compounds 6a-c might exhibit enhanced biological activity.

Several Mannich bases are known to possess pharmacological activities⁴, and this prompted us to synthesise 3-

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[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-4-methyl-1-(morpholinomethyl-/*p*-toluidinomethyl-)- Δ^2 -1,2,4-triazoline-5-thiones (7a,b). These compounds were obtained by condensation of 3a with formaldehyde in the presence of morpholine or *p*-toluidine.

Cyclodehydration of the thiosemicarbazides (2a-c) with phosphoric acid yielded 5-[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-2-(alkyl/arylamino)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (8a-c) in moderate yields.

R: a, CH₃; b, C₆H₅; c, C₆H₁₁ cyclo

Treatment of 1 with CS₂ in absolute ethanol containing KOH afforded potassium 3-[*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy]acetylthiocarbamate (9). Reaction of hydrazine hydrate with 9 afforded 4-amino-5-[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (10). Compound 10 was also prepared in much higher yield by the reaction of 5-[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol with hydrazine hydrate.

Interaction of 10 with aromatic aldehyde gave the azines (11a-f) instead of the expected Schiff bases. Moreover, reaction of 10 with *p*-substituted-phenacyl bromide gave the uncyclised products 12a-c rather than the expected cyclised products 13a-c.

Biological activity: Antimicrobial activities of several selected compounds were tested using cup-plate agar technique⁵ against *Pseudo-monas aeruginosa*, *Serratia rhodrii*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Micrococcus roseus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Most of the tested compounds exhibited no effect at concentration 1% (w/v). Com-

pounds 5b, 6c and 7a showed medium activity against *P. aeruginosa*. Also 5b exhibited medium activity and 10 showed strong activity against *S. aureus*.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian E11-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

(*p*-Benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)acetic acid hydrazide (1: 46%): It had m.p. 246° (Found: C, 63.52; H, 4.55; N, 19.44. C₁₅H₁₄N₄O₂ calcd. for: C, 63.82; H, 4.99; N, 19.84%).

p-(Benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)acetylthiosemicarbazides (2a-c): A mixture of 1 (2.8 g, 0.001 mol) and the appropriate isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was heated for 3-4 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 2a-c (90-95%): ν_{\max} 3 300-3 200 (NH), 1 700-1 680 (C=O), 1 620-1 600 (C=H), 1 280-1 250 cm⁻¹ (C=S); 2a, m.p. 270°; 2b, 160°, δ (DMSO-d₆) 10.3 (1H, s, CONH), 9.7 (2H, s, NHCSNH), 8.15-7.0 (13H, m, ArH), 4.7 (2H, s, OCH₂), NH signals exchangeable with D₂O; 2c, 236°.

5-[(*p*-Benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-4-alkylphenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiols (3a-c): Compound 2a-c (0.01 mol) dissolved in 2 *N* KOH (20 ml) was heated at 100° for 1 h and then filtered, cooled and acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to yield 3a-c (83-91%): ν_{\max} 3 450-3 350 (NH), 1 640-1 610 (C=N), 1 260-1 250 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 13.8-13.7 (1H, s, NH benzimidazole), 8.4-7.2 (8H, m, ArH), 5.4-5.3 (2H, s, OCH₂); 3a, m.p. 280°, δ 3.5 (1H, s, N-CH₂); 3b, 230°, δ 2.4-2.1 (1H, m, CH) and 2.0-1.0 (10H, m, (CH₂)₅, cyclohexyl).

5-[(*p*-Benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-3-alkylthio-1,2,4-triazoles (4a-c): To 3a (3.4 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in alcoholic KOH (20 ml; 4%) was added alkyl/aralkyl halide (0.01 mol) and the mixture was stirred for 1 h, refluxed at 100° for 2 h, then cooled and diluted with H₂O. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 4a-c (71-86%): ν_{\max} 3 300-3 150 (NH), 1 630-1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); 4a, m.p. 132-34°; 4b, 124-26°, δ (CDCl₃) 8.2-6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 5.25 (2H, s, OCH₂), 3.6 (3H, s, NCH₃), 3.3-3.05 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 1.5-1.3 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃); 4c, 206-08°.

Ethyl[5-[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl]thioacetate (4d) and/or malonate (4e): A mixture of 3a (0.3 g, 0.001 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.001 mol) and/or diethyl bromomalonate (0.01 mol) was refluxed in dry acetone (20 ml) containing K₂CO₃ (0.0015 mol) for 12 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water, and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to form 4d and 4e: 4d (96%), m.p. 175°, δ (CDCl₃) 8.11-7.0 (8H, m, ArH),

5.2 (2H, s, OCH₂), 4.2–4.0 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, SCH₂), 3.6 (3H, s, NCH₃), 1.2 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃); **4e** (80%), 150°, δ(CDCl₃) 8.5–6.9 (8H, m, ArH), 5.15 (2H, s, OCH₂), 5.0 (1H, s, SCH), 4.25–3.9 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₃), 3.6 (s, NCH₃), 1.3–1.0 (6H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₃); **4a** (71%), 132–34°; **b** (84%), 124–26°; **c** (86%), 206–08°.

5-[(*p*-Benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-4-methyl-3-phenacylthio-1,2,4-triazoles (**5a-c**): A mixture of **3a** (0.3 g, 0.001 mol) and *p*-substituted-phenacyl bromide (0.001 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (10 ml) for 3–4 h. The resulting solid was washed with K₂CO₃ solution and H₂O and crystallised from ethanol (yields 90–94%): ν_{max} 3 400–3 300 (NH), 1 690–1 680 (C=O) and 1 630–1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); **5a**, m.p. 245°; **b**, 257°, δ(DMSO-d₆) 8.3–7.3 (12H, m, ArH), 5.5–5.45 (2H, s, OCH₂), 4.9 (2H, s, SCH₂), 3.65 (3H, s, NCH₃); **c**, 240°.

5-[(*p*-Benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-3-carboxamidomethylthio-4-methyl-1,2,4-triazoles (**6a-c**): A mixture of **3a** (0.3 g, 0.001 mol) and *N*-chloroacetyl derivatives of aromatic and/or sulphapyridine (0.0012 mol) was refluxed in dry acetone (15 ml) containing K₂CO₃ (0.0015 mol) for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water and the resulting solid was washed with H₂O and crystallised from ethanol (yields 70–82%): ν_{max} 3 200–3 100 (NH), 1 680–1 670 cm⁻¹ (C=O); **6a**, m.p. 299°; **b**, 249°; **c**, 268°, δ(DMSO-d₆) 12.7 (1H, s, NH benzimidazole), 10.2 (1H, s, NHCO), 8.15–7.0 (12H, m, ArH), 5.4 (2H, s, OCH₂), 4.1 (2H, s, SCH₂), 3.75 (3H, s, NCH₃), 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃).

Mannich bases (**7a,b**): A mixture of **3a** (0.3 g, 0.001 mol) and morpholine or *p*-toluidine (0.001 mol) was refluxed in ethanol with formaldehyde (0.002 mol; 40%) for 2–3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from 50% ethanol: ν_{max} 3 400–3 200 (NH), 1 620–1 610 (C=N); **7a** (58%), m.p. 130°, δ(CDCl₃) 8.15–6.95 (8H, m, ArH), 5.15 (2H, s, OCH₂), 5.0 (2H, s, NCH₂N), 3.6 (3H, s, NCH₃), 3.7–3.55 (4H, m, CH₂OCH₂), 2.75–2.65 (4H, m, CH₂-N-CH₂); **b** (48%), 136°, δ(CDCl₃) 8.15–6.75 (12H, m, ArH), 5.5 (1H, t, NH, CH₂NH), 5.5 (2H, s, OCH₂), 5.05–5.0 (2H, d, NHCH₂N), 3.5 (3H, s, NCH₃), 2.15 (3H, s, CH₃).

2-[(*p*-Benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-2-alkyl/arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**8a-c**): Thiosemicarbazide **3a-c** (0.01 mol) was added to stirred phosphoric acid (20 ml) over 20 min at 120° and the mixture was stirred for 0.5 h and then poured in ice-water (400 ml). The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (yields 47–60%): ν_{max} 3 250–3 100 (NH), 1 620–1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); **8a**, m.p. 262°; **b**, 225°; **c**, 239°, δ(DMSO-d₆) 8.1–7.0 (8H, m, ArH), 5.3 (2H, s, OCH₂), 2.3–2.1 (1H, m, NH), 2.0–1.1 (10H, m, (CH₂)₅).

Potassium 3-[p-(benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)acetyl-dithiocarbazate] (**9**): It was prepared according to the reported procedure⁶ by the reaction of (*p*-benzimidazolylphenoxy)acetic acid hydrazide (2.8 g, 0.01 mol) with CS₂ (1.14 g, 0.015 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) containing KOH.

4-Amino-5-[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**10**): A suspension of **9** (0.02 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (95%; 1 g, 0.02 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (20 ml) for 8 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (2.7 g, 80.5%), m.p. 255–56° (Found: C, 56.59; H, 4.31; N, 24.64; S, 9.30. C₁₆H₁₄N₆OS calcd. for: C, 56.79; H, 4.17; N, 24.83; S, 9.47%).

Reaction of compound 10 with aromatic aldehydes: A mixture of **10** (0.3 g, 0.001 mol) and the appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.001 mol) was fused for 15 min or refluxed in ethanol (15 ml) containing few drops of piperidine as a basic catalyst for 3–4 h or refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid as yellow crystals of the azine derivatives (yields 49–52%): **11a**, m.p. 195°; **b**, 179°; **c**, 197°. The structures of **11a-f** were confirmed authentically in addition to their elemental and spectral data.

4-Amino-5-[(*p*-benzimidazol-2-ylphenoxy)methyl]-3-phenacylthio-1,2,4-triazoles (**12a-c**): A mixture of **10** (0.06 g, 0.002 mol) and *p*-substituted-phenacyl bromide (0.002 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (10 ml) for 3–5 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and the resulting solid was washed with K₂CO₃ solution and H₂O and crystallised from ethanol: ν_{max} 3 485–3 315 (NH₂), 3 190–3 180 (NH, benzimidazole), 1 680–1 670 (C=O) and 1 630–1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); **12a**, m.p. 240°; **b**, 228°; **c**, 235°, δ(DMSO-d₆) 8.1–7.0 (12H, m, ArH), 6.5 (2H, s, NH₂ exchangeable with D₂O), 5.2 (2H, s, OCH₂), 4.8 (2H, s, SCH₂).

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